

**Improving Recyclability of Thermoset Composite
Materials through a Greener Recycling Technology
based on Reversible Biobased Bonding Materials**

Research and Innovation Action (RIA)
Grant Agreement 101023190

**D6.1 “Project Website”
Work Package 6
Responsible Partner: Q-PLAN**

D6.1: Project Website

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Dissemination Level

PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the EC Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the EC Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the EC)	

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Executive Summary

This report with the title “Project Website” has been elaborated as a deliverable (D6.1) in the framework of the VIBES project, presenting the website of the project, as it was created within the first months of VIBES.

The VIBES project, funded by the Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme, aims to develop and demonstrate a new, greener, cost-efficient, and non-toxic recycling technology solution that resolves the end-of-life issues of thermoset composite materials.

The VIBES website (www.vibesproject.eu) serves as a platform for the communication and dissemination management of the project. It gathers the latest news, publications, events, external links, and social networks of VIBES to disseminate them among the targeted audience. Besides, it helps to create synergies with other projects and initiatives dealing with the same issues. The VIBES website also includes a section with a link to an internal platform restricted only to partners to manage a space where preliminary results and internal documents can be shared among project partners.

All partners will contribute to updating the VIBES website, by providing news about the project progress, information about events, and relevant articles and/ or documents that can be made available to the public, in order to be published on the project website.

1. Introduction

The current report on the VIBES website has been elaborated within the framework of the VIBES project, which is funded by the Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme, under Grant Agreement No 101023190.

The VIBES project aims to develop an innovative and cost-efficient green technology solution to resolve the end-of-life issues of thermoset composites, decreasing the amount of non-biodegradable polymers sent to disposal or discharged to the environment by at least 40%.

To reach its purpose, VIBES focuses on the controlled separation and recovery of composite material components by means of developing customised 100% Biobased Bonding Materials (BBM). In addition, the project designs and develops biobased thermoset composites, with the intention to place industrial biobased and recyclable substituent composite materials in the market. The developed materials will be validated for optimum performance/ cost ratio in 3 high-demand industrial sectors: aeronautical, construction and naval industries.

A greener, fast, economic, and non-toxic recycling technology to treat the smart VIBES composites will be developed and implemented at pilot semi-industrial environment. As a result, the recovered decomposed materials are to be valorised as new feedstocks for different chemicals or building blocks or for upscaling into new industrial products.

In this context, this report constitutes a detailed description of the VIBES website, presenting its functionalities that have been established for the needs of the project. The website will be optimised and enhanced with essential dissemination material, which is expected to serve as a multiplier of the project's main goals and objectives.

With that in mind, this report encompasses the following:

- **Chapter 1** briefly describes the VIBES project and introduces its website.
- **Chapter 2** describes the VIBES website that has been created to support all the necessary horizontal activities of the project.
- **Chapter 3** specifies the conclusions resulting from the development of the deliverable.

2. VIBES website

The VIBES website is publicly available at <http://www.vibesproject.eu/> and it was designed during the early stages of the project, in order to support all the necessary horizontal activities of the project. The VIBES website is based on a common layout that is responsive and guarantees easy browsing through the site's web pages. More specifically the layout is presented in Figure 1, Figure 2 and Figure 3 and consists of:

- The **Header** section, which contains the project logo and its acronym, as well as the **Main Navigation Menu**, which facilitates the fast browsing between the different sections of the website.
- The **Main Content Area**, the main part of every page, presenting the users' information requested.
- The **Footer** containing the social media links, the structure of the website (sitemap) and the information about the project's funding by the Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme.

Figure 1. VIBES website layout (top)

In a Nutshell

The VIBES project presents an innovative solution to resolve the end-of-life issues of thermoset composite materials, based on the development of a new green technology, focused on the controlled separation and recovery of composite material components by means of developing customised biobased bonding materials (BBM).

Figure 2. VIBES website layout (centre)

Figure 3. VIBES website layout (bottom)

The content and structure of the VIBES website was organised and designed to showcase the project, in terms of concept and objectives, activities, consortium partners and stakeholders, resources as well as the presentation of news related to VIBES work. Site visits, statistics and other information on visitor’s views (e.g. number of pages per visit, time on site, most viewed pages, etc.) will be measured using Google Analytics. The following list presents the main sections of the website, which are further analysed in the following subsections:

- **Home:** The homepage holds a header menu as well as the project’s aim and overall concept in a nutshell, a promotional video of the project, a slider with the project partners, the project’s latest news, and the newsletter subscription form. The main purpose of this page is to summarise the project offerings and current state in a glance.
- **About:** This section aims to present briefly all the important information related to the project. More specifically, the subsections are presented below:

- **Concept and Objectives:** This section presents VIBES concept, the problem to be tackled and the approach to be taken in order to develop the respective solutions.
- **Consortium Partners:** The purpose of this section is to present the project's consortium.
- **Stakeholders:** This section briefly describes the whole value chain of the VIBES project and highlights the importance of getting feedback and guidance from various stakeholder representatives that constitute the VIBES Stakeholders Board.
- **Activities:** This section outlines the main activities of the project that will be implemented in order to reach its objectives.
- **Resources:** This section is set on giving access to the project's public reports, publications, training and promotional material as well as links to relevant events and other related projects. It includes the following subsections:
 - **Reports:** List of public deliverables together with download links for each one after their successful completion.
 - **Publications:** List of publications stemming from the scientific research conducted by the project partners in the framework of VIBES, including an electronic copy of each published manuscript deposited on the project website either as a reproduction (if permitted) or as a direct link to the publication.
 - **Training material:** List of the training material developed for the training activities of the project, which can be publicly accessible.
 - **Promotional material:** List of the promotional material (leaflets, infographic etc.) developed for the communication and dissemination of the project.
 - **Other links:** Lists of a) several relevant events (meetings and conferences), and b) other related projects, along with the links to their individual websites.
- **News & Events:** This subsection aims to serve as the main getaway to the project's news as well as give access to the VIBES newsletter. It includes the following subsections:
 - **Project developments:** List of news related to the development of the project, with a view to sharing experiences and achievements between the partners and the community of the website users.
 - **Dissemination and training events:** List of news, focusing specifically on the events organised in the course of the project for dissemination and training (international events, workshops, roundtables, conference, training programme).
 - **Newsletters:** In this subsection, the website visitors can see all the project newsletters as well as subscribe to the project's newsletter in order to receive future editions through mail when they are available. The project's newsletter is delivered through the Mailchimp tool (<https://mailchimp.com/>).
 - **Press Releases:** List of the press releases issued in English for the communication and dissemination of the project.

- **Contact us:** In this section, the website visitors are able to communicate with the project’s communication manager either by sending an email to the general VIBES email address (info@vibesproject.eu) or by filling out their comment/ query in a dedicated form.
- **Privacy Policy:** This section contains the Privacy and Cookies Policy of the VIBES website (Annex I).
- **Private Area:** This section includes a link to an internal platform, restricted only to members of the project consortium, managing a space where preliminary results and internal documents can be shared among project partners.

About > Concept and objectives

- Concept and objectives
- Consortium partners
- Stakeholders
- Activities

In a Nutshell

The VIBES project presents an innovative solution to resolve the end-of-life issues of thermoset composite materials, based on the development of a new green technology, focused on the controlled separation and recovery of composite material components by means of developing customised biobased bonding materials (BBM).

VIBES is a research & innovation project, with a duration of 48 months and a budget of almost 5.3 million Euros, funded by Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking (BBI - JU) under the European Union’s Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, Horizon 2020.

Why VIBES?

The use of composite materials has gained interest in recent years due to their unique properties such as high mechanical strength, good chemical resistance and long durability, as well as great lightness and corrosion resistance. Their properties make them very attractive for a large number of applications in many high technology sectors, such as aeronautics, automotive, construction, marine and naval, energy, sports, electronics etc.

However, the end-of-life of thermoset composites in particular poses a technical difficulty due to their inherent complexity, generating plastic waste. Currently most of the thermoset composite waste is not properly recycled and it is either incinerated (42.6%) or diverted to landfill (24.9%). Industrial needs for high performance materials have increased the use of composite materials, so there is a need to develop and ensure a systematic circular ecosystem for these materials as a priority in Europe, in order to be able to contribute to the EU's 2050 long-term strategy for a climate-neutral Europe.

VIBES Approach

The VIBES project will develop and demonstrate a new, greener, cost-efficient, and non-toxic recycling technology solution that aims to decrease the amount of non-biodegradable polymers sent to disposal or discharged to the environment by at least 40%. Once this technology has been optimised and scaled-up to a pilot semi-industrial environment, the products obtained from the new recycling process will return to the market by means of their valorisation as new feedstocks for different chemicals or building blocks and by upcycling into new industrial products.

Benefits will be significant in terms of growth, increasing jobs and turnover by promoting two new industrial sector interconnections in the newly created "Intrinsic Recyclable Thermoset Composites Value Chain" (between waste management and biotechnology sectors; between thermoset composites and biotechnology sectors).

Figure 4. VIBES concept and objectives webpage

Consortium Partners

Research & Technology Organisations

FUNDACION AITIIP
Project Coordinator

Spain

CONDICIONAMIENTO
TARRASENSE ASSOCIACION

Spain

DEUTSCHE INSTITUTE FÜR
TEXTIL-FASERFORSCHUNG
UND FASERFORSCHUNG DENKENDORF

Germany

Academic Institution

UNIVERSITY OF LIMERICK
Bernal Institute

Ireland

Industrial Developers

SPECIFIC
POLYMERS

France

WEVERIJ FLIPTS
EN DOBBELS NV

Belgium

BCIRCULAR COMPOSITES
SOCIEDAD LIMITADA

Spain

JUNO
COMPOSITES LTD

Ireland

INGENIERIA Y DESARROLLOS
EN COMPOSITE S.L.

Spain

Industrial Users

CONSORCIO AERODROMO
AEROPUERTO DE TERUEL

Spain

ACCIONA
CONSTRUCCION SA

Spain

Technology Consultant

LABORATORI
ARCHA SRL

Italy

Innovation Management Consultant

Q-PLAN
INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC

Greece

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- Activities

Resources

- Reports
- Publications
- Training material
- Promotional material
- Other links

News & Events

- Project developments
- Dissemination and training events
- Newsletters
- Press Releases

Contact us

[Privacy Policy](#)

[PRIVATE AREA](#)

This project has received funding from the Bio-based Industries Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme, under Grant Agreement N° 101022950.

Figure 5. VIBES consortium partners webpage

Stakeholders

To solve the end-of-life issues of thermoset composites and reduce the negative impact of composites waste in the environment, collaborative innovation in the complex economic and technical ecosystem is essential. All the players in the composites value chain must be involved.

The VIBES project covers the whole value chain by taking into account, apart from the consortium partners, the Stakeholders Board and interaction with other projects of Biobased Industries through communication and dissemination activities.

VIBES stakeholders in the whole value chain

INDUSTRIAL DEVELOPERS

Thermoset Composite Developers

Composite Recyclers

INDUSTRIAL CONVERTERS, DISMANTLERS & END-USERS

Aeronautical

Naval

Construction

Energy

Waste Management

Logistics

Transport

TECHNOLOGY & INNOVATION EXPERTS

Academic / Researchers

Technology and / or Innovation Consultants

IMPACT MULTIPLIERS

Policy Makers

Media / Journalists or Bloggers

Stakeholders Board

The Stakeholders Board includes individuals from the whole value chain, either independent or representing organisations, who are external to the consortium partners. The members of the Stakeholders Board collaborate in the project to effectively respond to market and social needs, give feedback and better guide decisions in the project. They are industry-led, while fostering public and private collaboration.

Figure 6. VIBES stakeholders' webpage

Activities

The VIBES consortium achieves the project objectives by collaborating in the following activities:

Design and development of at least three 100% biobased bonding materials (BBM) for thermoset composites with tailored debonding functionalities.

Design and development of at least three 100% biobased thermoset composite materials, one per type of industrial sector.

Validation of the developed composite materials with intrinsic recycling properties in relation to optimum performance / cost ratio for three high-demand industrial sectors: aeronautical, construction and naval industries.

Design and pilot implementation of VIBES green recycling technology to separate and valorise the composite components as new feedstocks for the development of new products.

Sustainability and economical assessment of the developed VIBES products.

Exploitation & IPR strategy for Key Exploitable Results.

Development of a Business Plan to demonstrate the commercial potential of VIBES technology and describe how this potential will be realised.

Communication and dissemination activities, aiming at informing, promoting, communicating and disseminating the project objectives, activities and results, as well as engaging stakeholders and creating synergies.

Training activities, aiming at providing knowledge and skills to industry, students and open society.

This project has received funding from the Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking under the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme, under Grant Agreement N° 101022390.

Figure 7. VIBES activities webpage

Contact us

info@vibesproject.eu

Project Coordinator:
FUNDACION ATIIP
Poligono Industrial Empresarium
Calle Romero N°12
50720 Zaragoza, Spain

Communication, Training & Stakeholders Manager:
Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC
11 El. Venizelou str.
55133 Kalamaria, Thessaloniki
Greece

Please send us your message by completing this form:

Your Name (optional)

Your Email (required)

Subject (required)

Your Message (required)

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Figure 8. VIBES contact us webpage

The web pages of the **Resources** sub menu (Reports, Publications, Training material, Promotional material, Other links) and the **News & Events** sub menu (Project developments, Dissemination and training events, Newsletters, Press Releases) have no content at the time of this report, except from short messages indicating that the page will be populated once content is available, and as such it is not considered meaningful to provide their screenshots.

The content of the **Privacy Policy** is presented in **Annex I**.

3. Conclusions

This report has presented the website of the VIBES project as part of a multi-dimensional communication and dissemination approach. The communication and dissemination approach of VIBES addresses all relevant target groups and raises public awareness about the solutions to be created, developed and demonstrated in the framework of VIBES, with a view to paving the way for their successful rollout and uptake beyond the end of the project.

Annex I. VIBES Privacy Policy

1. Who we are

The VIBES project, funded by Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking (BBI – JU) under the European Union’s Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, Horizon 2020, aims to develop an innovative and cost-efficient green technology solution to resolve the end-of-life issues of thermoset composites, decreasing the amount of non-biodegradable polymers sent to disposal or discharged to the environment by at least 40%.

To reach its purpose, VIBES focuses on the controlled separation and recovery of composite material components by means of developing customised 100% Biobased Bonding Materials (BBM). In addition, the project designs and develops biobased thermoset composites, with the intention to place industrial biobased and recyclable substituent composite materials in the market. The developed materials will be validated for optimum performance/ cost ratio in 3 high-demand industrial sectors: aeronautical, construction and naval industries.

A greener, fast, economic, and non-toxic recycling technology to treat the smart VIBES composites is under development and implementation at pilot semi-industrial environment. As a result, the recovered decomposed materials are to be valorised as new feedstocks for different chemicals or building blocks or for upscaling into new industrial products.

The project partners of the VIBES consortium, listed below, process certain types of personal data for the purposes of the project. Each partner is responsible for the personal data they collect and process during their activities under the framework of the project:

- FUNDACION AITIIP (Project Coordinator), Spain, <https://www.aitiip.com/>
- SPECIFIC POLYMERS, France, <https://specificpolymers.com/>
- ACONDICIONAMIENTO TARRASENSE ASSOCIACION, Spain, <https://www.leitat.org/>
- UNIVERSITY OF LIMERICK, Bernal Institute, Ireland, <https://bernalinstitute.com/>
- DEUTSCHE INSTITUTE FUR TEXTIL UND FASERFORSCHUNG DENKENDORF, Germany, <https://www.ditf.de/en/>
- WEVERIJ FLIPTS EN DOBBELS NV, Belgium, <https://flaxco.be/>
- BCIRCULAR COMPOSITES SOCIEDAD LIMITADA, Spain, <https://www.bcircular.com/>
- CONSORCIO AERODROMO AEROPUERTO DE TERUEL, Spain, <http://www.aeropuertodeteruel.com/en/>
- ACCIONA CONSTRUCCION SA, Spain, <https://www.acciona.com/>
- INGENIERIA Y DESARROLLOS EN COMPOSITE S.L., Spain, <http://www.idec.aero/>
- JUNO COMPOSITES LTD, Ireland, <https://junocomposites.com/>
- LABORATORI ARCHA SRL, Italy, <http://www.archa.it/>
- Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC (Communication, Training & Stakeholders Manager), Greece, <https://qplan-intl.gr/>

For further information, we can be contacted at: info@vibesproject.eu.

2. How we collect your personal data

We collect personal data both directly and indirectly:

- We obtain personal data directly from individuals in a variety of ways, including but not limited to the following cases:
 - an individual subscribes to our newsletter/s;
 - an individual registers to attend in meetings, workshops and other events we host and during attendance at such events;
 - we establish cooperative relationships with an individual;
 - we provide professional services pursuant to our contract with the European Commission;
- We obtain personal data indirectly about individuals from a variety of sources, including:
 - our research partners;
 - our networks and contacts;
 - public and open data sources such as public registers, news articles and internet searches;
 - social and professional networking sites (e.g. LinkedIn).

3. What types of data we collect

We only collect the data that are necessary for the smooth implementation of our project. These data fall into the following categories:

- contact details (name/ surname, e-mail address, street address, mobile phone number, land line phone number);
- professional information (job title, organization, field of expertise);
- demographics (e.g. age, gender, nationality);
- information about what a person knows or believes;
- videos and photos (from people that attend our events).

4. Bases of lawful processing

We process personal data on the following legal bases:

- Legal obligations – for processing activities required for compliance both with applicable national and European legislation as well as with the specific legal and regulatory framework of the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme for Research and Innovation of the European Union.
- Consent – for processing activities such as organisation of meetings, workshops, other events, and dissemination of project's results.
- Contractual obligations – for processing activities such as reporting to the European Commission and complying with project's publicity obligations.

5. What we do with your personal data

We process your personal data with the purpose of:

- Disseminating our project's results to different types of stakeholders;
- Sending invitations and providing access to guests attending our meetings, events and workshops;
- Administering, maintaining, and ensuring the security of our information systems, applications, and websites;
- Processing online requests or queries, including responding to communications from individuals;

- Complying with contractual, legal, and regulatory obligations.

6. How we secure your personal data when we process it

We continuously apply a personal data risk assessment process to identify, analyse, and evaluate the security risks that may threaten your personal data. Based on the results of this risk assessment, we define and apply a set of both technical and organizational measures to mitigate the above security risks, including but not limited to:

- Data Protection Policies to guide personnel involved in the VIBES Project when processing your data;
- Written contracts with organisations that process personal data on our behalf;
- Non-Disclosure Agreements with personnel of the VIBES consortium partners;
- Back up process, antimalware protection, access control mechanisms, etc.
- Some of VIBES partners have appointed a Data Protection Officer.

7. Do we share personal data with third parties?

We may occasionally share personal data with trusted third parties to help us deliver efficient and quality services. When we do so, we ensure that recipients are contractually bound to safeguard the data we entrust to them before we share the data. We may engage with several or all of the following categories of recipients:

- Parties that support us as we provide our services (e.g., cloud-based software services such as Dropbox, Microsoft Sharepoint, Google);
- Our professional advisers, including lawyers, auditors, and insurers;
- Dissemination service providers (e.g., MailChimp);
- Law enforcement or other government and regulatory agencies or other third parties as required by, and in accordance with applicable law or regulation;
- The European Commission according to our relevant contractual obligations.

8. Do we transfer your personal data outside the European Economic Area?

We do not own file servers located outside the European Economic Area (EEA). However, some partners may use cloud and / or marketing services from reputable providers such as SharePoint, DropBox, MailChimp, Google, etc., situated both inside and outside the EEA. We always check that such providers comply with the relevant GDPR requirements before start using their services.

9. Do we use cookies?

Our website, <https://www.vibesproject.eu>, uses cookies. We use cookies to improve site navigation, and to analyse our traffic. In the next paragraphs you will learn what cookies are, what cookies we use and how you can disable their use.

Cookies are small alphanumeric characters files that are transferred from websites that you visit to your PC, smartphone, tablet or any other electronic device that you use for browsing. Cookies assign your computer with a unique ID, which in turn becomes your own identity each time you return to a website. Cookies do not damage your electronic equipment, nor can they read information from other files on your computer's hard drive.

Websites use cookies to “remember” for a period your actions and preferences such as language, font size and other display features. In this way you are not required to enter these preferences each time you visit a

website and navigate in its pages. Furthermore, cookies help websites owners to analyse how you are using their website whether or not you are facing problems as you navigate in them.

Personal Data protection legislation states that we can store cookies on your device if they are strictly necessary for the operation of our website. For all other types of cookies, we need your consent. You can change or withdraw your consent at any time from the Cookies Settings on our website.

In our website, <https://www.vibesproject.eu/>, we use necessary, statistics and functional cookies. Some cookies are placed by third party services (e.g. Google analytics).

Without necessary cookies the website cannot perform its basic functions. These cookies are generally placed automatically either when a webpage is loaded or as a result of a user’s request (that cannot be fulfilled without using a relevant cookie). Usually, necessary cookies expire when you close your browser.

Statistics cookies help us to measure our website’s traffic and where it comes from, so that we can improve its performance. Moreover, they collect information about which pages are more popular and on how visitors use our website. None of this information can be used to identify you. It is all aggregated and, therefore, anonymized. This category includes cookies from third-party analytics services such as Google Analytics. Our website uses the following statistics cookies:

Name	Provider	Purpose	Expiry
_ga	Google analytics	This cookie is used to distinguish unique users by assigning a randomly generated number as a client identifier. It is included in each page request in a site and used to calculate visitor, session and campaign data for the site’s analytics reports.	2 years
_gid	Google analytics	This cookie stores and updates a unique value for each page visited. It is used to generate statistical data on how the visitor uses the web site. It collects anonymized data including the number and origin of visitors and the websites they visited.	1 day
_gat	Google analytics	This cookie is used to throttle request rate, that is limiting the collection of data on high traffic sites.	1 minute

Functionality cookies allow websites to remember the user’s site preferences and choices they make on the site including username, region, and language. This allows the website to provide personalized features if you share your location. They are anonymous and do not track browsing activity across other websites.

You can delete cookies and stop them from being installed in your browser. There is no standardized way to remove cookies since different browsers clear cookies using different procedures. Please follow the instructions provided by each browser manufacturer on how to remove cookies.

If you wish to stop sending your information to Google Analytics, you may install in your browser the Google Analytics Opt-out Browser Add-on.

You may select and change the cookie settings (with the exception of the technically necessary cookies) by clicking on Cookie settings. By making a cookie active, you consent to its use according to the provisions of this Cookies Policy.

10. Your rights

You have the following rights regarding our processing of your personal data:

- Right to withdraw consent – You can withdraw consent that you have previously given to one or more specified purposes to process your personal data. This will not affect the lawfulness of any processing carried out before you withdraw your consent.
- Right of access – You can ask us to verify whether we are processing personal data about you and, if so, to have access to a copy of such data.
- Right to rectification and erasure – You can ask us to correct our records if you believe they contain incorrect or incomplete information about you or ask us to erase your personal data after you withdraw your consent to processing or when we no longer need it for the purpose it was originally collected.
- Right to restriction of processing – You can ask us to temporarily restrict our processing of your personal data if you contest the accuracy of your personal data, prefer to restrict its use rather than having us erase it, or need us to preserve it for you to establish, exercise or defend a legal claim. A temporary restriction may apply while verifying whether we have overriding legitimate grounds to process it. You can ask us to inform you before we lift that temporary processing restriction.
- Right to data portability – In some circumstances, where you have provided personal data to us, you can ask us to transmit that personal data (in a structured, commonly used, and machine-readable format) directly to another entity.
- Right to object – You can object to our use of your personal data for direct marketing purposes, including profiling or where processing has taken the form of automated decision-making. However, we may need to keep some minimal information (e.g., e-mail address) to comply with your request to cease marketing to you.
- Right to make a complaint to your local Data Protection Authority (DPA) (see https://ec.europa.eu/justice/article-29/structure/data-protection-authorities/index_en.htm) regarding any concerns you may have about our data handling practices.

To ask us to do anything of the above, you can contact us by email: info@vibesproject.eu. We will promptly examine your request against the relevant requirements of the laws and regulations governing privacy and personal data protection and we will answer the latest within 30 days after receiving your request. We will ask from you some kind of identification (e.g. photocopy of your identity card or passport) to avoid non-authorized reveal of your personal data. If, for reasons of complexity of the request or a multitude of requests, we are unable to respond promptly, we will notify you within 30 days of any delay, which in no case may exceed two months from the expiration of the 30-day deadline.

11. How long do we retain personal data?

We retain personal data to provide our services, stay in contact with you and to comply with applicable laws, regulations, and contractual obligations to which we are subject. Please note that we have an obligation to

retain data concerning projects funded by the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme for Research and Innovation of the European Union for up to five years after the end of the project (unless further retention is requested by auditors). After the expiry of the retention period, and unless further legitimate grounds for retention arise, we will dispose of personal data in a secure manner.

12. Disclaimer of liability for third party websites

Although our site may contain links to third-party sites, including the sites of the VIBES consortium partners, we are not responsible for the privacy practices or content of these sites and we expressly disclaim any liability for any loss or damage that may be caused by the use of these links. We do not monitor the privacy practices or the content of these sites. If you have any questions about the privacy practices of another site, you should contact the site's responsible personnel. We suggest you read the privacy policy of each website you interact with, before allowing the collection and use of your personal data.

We may also provide social media features that allow you to share information on your social networks and interact with the VIBES project on various social media sites. The use of these social media features may result in the collection or sharing of information about you. We recommend that you check the privacy policies and regulations of the social networking sites you interact with, so that you can be sure that you understand what information may be collected, used and disclosed by these sites.

13. Children

We do not knowingly collect, use, or disclose information from children under the age of 16. If we learn that we have collected the personal information of a child under 16 we will take steps to delete the information as soon as possible. Please immediately contact us if you become aware that a child under 16 has provided us with personal information.

14. Revisions of this Privacy Policy

This Privacy Policy is valid from 5/07/2021 and replaces any other previous notifications that we had issued in the past regarding our personal data management practices. We reserve the right to revise this Policy at any time. The current version will be always uploaded to our website indicating the date of entry into force, so you know when the most recent revision took place. If there are critical changes in this policy or our personal data practices change significantly in the future, we will notify you by posting the changes on our website.